

DYES DERIVED FROM ACENAPHTHENEQUINONE. PART XII.
2-(4-CHLORO)-THONAPHTHENE-ACENAPHTHYLENE-INDIGOS

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Acenaphthenequinone and a few of its substituted products and also phenanthraquinone have been condensed with 4-chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene. The colour and the dyeing shade of 2-(4-chloro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos, prepared now, have been compared with those of the corresponding compounds of the 5-, 6- and 7-chloro series, previously studied. The change in colour in relation to chemical constitution of the isomeric 4-, 5-, 6- and 7-chloro dyes of the acenaphthenequinone series has been established.

In Parts VII, X and XI of this series (Guha, this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 127, Guha and Chatterjea, *ibid.*, 1948, 25, 429; Guha and Sinha, *ibid.*, 1952, 29, 415), 2-(5-chloro)-, 2-(7-chloro)- and 2-(6-chloro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos were prepared and a comparative study of their colour change was made. In this communication 2-(4-chloro)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos have been prepared with a view to completing the study of the influence of a chlorine atom in all the four available positions (4, 5, 6 & 7) of the thionaphthene ring of Ciba Scarlet G, Ciba Red R etc., and also for the purpose of comparing these isomeric (chloro) thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos with those of the corresponding compounds of the isomeric (methyl) thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigo series, already studied from the point of view of the relation between colour and chemical constitution (Guha, *ibid.*, 1933, 10, 679; 1936, 13, 94; 1938, 15, 20; 1943, 20, 37).

4-Chloro-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Guha, Chatterjea and Sinha, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 777; cf. Dalglish and Mann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 900) was condensed with acenaphthenequinone, its 3-chloro, 3-bromo and β -methoxy derivatives. The structure (I) represents the general constitution of the new series of thioindigoid dyes described here.

These dyes of 4-chloro series are all soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene and aniline and sparingly soluble in acetic acid, acetone, carbon tetrachloride and alcohol. They also dissolve in strong sulphuric acid producing deep green solutions which, when kept exposed to atmosphere, gradually absorb moisture and change to blue, violet and finally precipitates the original red substance. The parent compound and its 3'-chloro and 3'-bromo derivatives imparted to cotton a pleasant bright red, red and deep red shade from

an alkaline hydrosulphite violet vat at 50°-60°, but the 1'-methoxy derivative, behaving similarly to the isomeric methoxy compounds of 5-, 6-, and 7-chloro series, offered resistance to reduction and imparted a pink shade only, even after prolonged attempt (cf. Guha, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 787).

A comparison of colour and the dyeing shades on cotton of compounds of this 4-chloro series with those of 5-, 6- and 7-chloro series and also the joint study of the spectrophotometric measurements of some of the dyes of the four isomeric chloro series (Figs. 1 and 2) indicate conclusively that the colour change is in the order: 5-chloro dye > 4-chloro dye > 7-chloro dye > 6-chloro dye (Table I). This observation is similar to those of the isomeric 2-(4-, 5-, 6-, & 7-methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos. But here, the position of the mother compound, Ciba scarlet G, comes next to its 6-chloro derivative unlike its relationship to the isomeric (methyl) thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos (Guha, *loc. cit.*).

In Tables I and II, T denotes thionaphthene and AI denotes acenaphthylene-indigo.

TABLE I

Compounds.	Dyeing shade on cotton.	Absorption maxima.
2-(5-Chloro)T-AI	Dark red (with violet tinge)	5190 Å
2-(4-Chloro)T-AI	Pleasant bright red	5120
2-(7-Chloro)T-AI	Red	5090
2-(6-Chloro)T-AI	Deep orange-red	5050
2-T-AI (Ciba scarlet G)	Scarlet-red	4775
2-(5-Chloro)T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	Pink	5250
2-(4-Chloro)T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	Pink (lighter shade)	5160
2-(7-Chloro)T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	Pink (do)	5140
2-(6-Chloro)T-8'-(1'-methoxy)-AI	Faint pink	5100

Another thioindigoid dye, 2-(4-chloro)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo (II) was prepared. It is soluble in nitrobenzene, aniline and pyridine and moderately soluble in benzene, toluene, xylene, glacial acetic acid and acetone. The alkaline hydrosulphite yellow vat of this compound was produced at 50-55°, from which cotton was dyed in uniform shade [cf. 2-(5-, 6-chloro)-thionaphthene-9'-phenanthrene-indigo; Guha, *loc. cit.* Guha and Sinha, *loc. cit.*].

TABLE II

Name.	Mol. formula.	Reactants and glacial acetic acid used.*	Appearance and M.P.	Yield.	Solubility.	Dyeing shade on cotton.	Found.	Calc.
2-(4-Chloro)-T-AI	$C_{22}H_9O_2ClS$	B (0.455 g.) + C (0.46 g.) in 39 c.c.	Yellowish red small needles from benzene; 290-91°.	0.8 g. (91.8%)	Benzene, toluene, xylene.	Pleasant bright red	Cl: 10.01% C: 68.7 H: 2.5	10.18% 68.8 2.5
2-(4-Chloro)-T-8' 8'(3'-chloro)-AI	$C_{20}H_7O_2Cl_2S$	3-Chloro-B (0.54 g.) + C (0.46 g.) in 45 c.c.	Red mica like plates from xylene; 289-91°.	0.85 g (88.8%)	Xylene; moderately in toluene; sparingly in benzene.	Red	Cl: 18.56 S: 8.2	18.54 8.3
2-(4-Chloro)-T-8' (3'-bromo)-AI	$C_{20}H_7O_2ClBrS$	3-Bromo-B (0.65 g.) + C (0.46 g.) in 45 c.c.	Do; 284-85°	0.9 g (84.2%)	Soluble in xylene; moderately in benzene & toluene.	Pleasant deep red	Br: 18.85 Cl: 8.34	18.71 8.3
2-(4-Chloro)-T-8' -(1'-methoxy)-AI	$C_{21}H_{11}O_2ClS$	β -Methoxy-B (0.64 g.) + C (0.55 g.) in 70 c.c.	Tufts of deep red small needles from nitrobenzene; 325°	0.77 g (67.6%)	Sparingly in benzene	Pink	Cl: 9.28 S: 8.58	9.37 8.45
2-(4-Chloro)-T-8' 9'-phenanthrene-indigo	$C_{22}H_9O_2ClS$	Phenanthroquinone (0.62 g.) + C (0.55 g.) in 40 c.c.	Violet globular crystalline aggregate from benzene; 284-286° shrinking at 268°.	0.48 g (41.7%)	Sparingly in CCl_4 and alcohol	Reddish violet	Cl: 9.64 S: 8.4	9.47 8.54

* B denotes acenaphthenequinone; C denotes 4-chloro-3-hydroxy-thionaphthene

FIG. 2

Curves A-D represent respectively 2-(4-, 5-, 6- and 7-chloro)-thionaphthene-8-(1'-methoxy)-acnaphthylene-indigos.

FIG. 1

Curves I-IV represent respectively 2-(4-, 5-, 6- & 7-chloro)-thionaphthene-acnaphthylene-indigos.

* E X P E R I M E N T A L

The thioindigoid dyes described in Table II were prepared in the usual manner by dissolving the molecular proportion of the constituents in glacial acetic acid and boiling for 20-30 minutes only with the addition of HCl (conc., 2-3 c.c.). These were filtered hot, washed with acetic acid, hot water and crystallised.

The light absorption measurements in the visible region were determined in xylene solutions.

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* All m.p. s recorded are uncorrected.